

AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF FINTECH INNOVATIONS IN INSURANCE: ADOPTION PATTERNS, SERVICE EFFICIENCY, AND USER CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of fintech innovations on individuals with respect to financial protection through insurance. The research is based on primary data collected from 135 respondents in South Gujarat using a structured questionnaire. The study evaluates awareness, adoption, customer experience, and challenges associated with digital insurance platforms. Using descriptive and exploratory research design, the study identifies that fintech has significantly improved accessibility, transparency, and efficiency in insurance services. However, issues such as claim delays, technical challenges, and lack of personal interaction continue to affect user satisfaction. The findings highlight that fintech-driven insurance is a key contributor to financial inclusion and risk protection, but requires further improvements for sustainable growth.

Keywords: *Fintech, InsurTech, Digital Insurance, Financial Protection, Customer Experience.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of financial technology (FinTech) has transformed the insurance sector, known as InsurTech. Traditional insurance systems were burdened with complex procedures, excessive paperwork, limited reach, and slow claim processes. FinTech has modernized this framework by integrating technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, blockchain, cloud computing, mobile applications, and the Internet of Things (IoT), making insurance more accessible, affordable, transparent, and customer-focused.

FinTech has significantly improved accessibility and financial inclusion by eliminating geographical barriers through digital platforms and mobile applications, enabling rural and underserved populations to access insurance services. It has also enhanced affordability and customization. Customer experience and service efficiency have improved, allowing policyholders to compare, purchase, renew, and manage policies online. AI-powered chatbots

provide instant support, while automation, AI, and blockchain have made claims management faster, more transparent, and secure.

Additionally, IoT and wearable technology support proactive risk management by monitoring real-time data. FinTech has also increased financial literacy through easy access to information and educational resources. Despite benefits, challenges like data privacy, cybersecurity risks, and regulatory issues remain, though FinTech continues to strengthen financial protection through insurance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review highlights the significant transformation of the insurance sector through FinTech and InsurTech innovations, as discussed by various researchers. Studies by Thakur, Rasool, Palhad, and Khan (2022) emphasize that the rise of InsurTech, driven by technologies like AI, is disrupting traditional insurance systems and creating new skill requirements in the industry. Similarly, Adelio Ikonomi (2022) explains how artificial intelligence enhances pricing, fraud detection, and claims processing while also introducing challenges such as high costs and algorithmic risks.

Research by Shamsuddin (2024) shows that InsurTech adoption positively impacts firm performance and financial sustainability, while Arner, Barberis, and Buckley (2015) describe the evolution of FinTech and its role in reshaping financial services globally. Arthur Charpentier further highlights the changing relationships between insurers, BigTech firms, and InsurTech companies in the digital era.

Several studies focus on operational efficiency and customer experience. Archit Pratap Gupta (2024) explains how FinTech reduces administrative costs and improves claim processing through automation, while Dr. Gayathiry D and Mrs. Suganya D (2023) find that customers have a positive attitude toward digital insurance due to convenience and time-saving benefits. Maryam Muzahem Abbas (2025) also confirms that FinTech improves efficiency but faces challenges like resistance to change and lack of training.

The role of digital transformation and collaboration is emphasized by Marto Barroso and Juan Laborda (2022), highlighting the importance of regulation and cooperation between FinTech firms and traditional institutions. Svitlana Volosovych (2021) notes that the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated digital adoption in insurance, while Paulin Kamuangu (2024) stresses the need to address data privacy and regulatory challenges for sustainable growth.

Other researchers such as Munir Abu Shower (2024) and Mohit S Reddy, Dr. Kiran Kumar (2024) underline the broad impact of FinTech across financial sectors. Overall, FinTech has improved accessibility, efficiency, and customer-centricity in insurance, despite challenges like cybersecurity risks, data privacy concerns, regulatory issues, and lack of digital literacy.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology adopts a systematic approach to analyze the impact of FinTech innovations on individuals' financial protection through insurance, based on a clear problem statement focusing on how technology-driven solutions have transformed the insurance sector. The study aims to understand the impact of FinTech tools on customers, examine how technology-driven processes improve efficiency in the insurance sector, and study the challenges of InsurTech on individuals. The hypothesis states that H0 indicates no impact, while H1 suggests there is an impact of FinTech innovations on financial protection through insurance. The research design combines exploratory and descriptive approaches, where exploratory research identifies emerging trends such as AI-driven underwriting, digital onboarding, and micro-insurance, and descriptive research analyzes improvements in customer experience through faster claim settlements, seamless policy management, and enhanced transparency. Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of multiple choice, dichotomous, multiple response, and 5-point Likert scale questions to gain insights into customer behaviour, perception, and satisfaction. The study employs non-probability sampling techniques, including judgmental, convenience, and snowball sampling, with a sample of 135 respondents from the South Gujarat Region selected based on their familiarity with FinTech-based insurance services. Despite limitations such as limited respondent awareness and the rapidly evolving nature of FinTech, the methodology provides a structured and reliable framework for analyzing the research problem.

4. DATA ANALYSIS& INTERPRETATION

Data analysis is the process of organizing, summarizing, and examining collected data in order to draw meaningful conclusions and answer the research objectives. It involves classifying, tabulating, and interpreting data to identify patterns, trends, and relationships.

Awareness of fintech-based insurance is extremely high among respondents, indicating strong digital penetration, effective promotion, and increasing familiarity with online platforms, which creates a favourable environment for further growth and adoption of digital insurance.

Table: 1 Reference of applications of respondents

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Friends	27	12
Insurance application	16	7
WhatsApp	34	15
YouTube	17	8
Not applicable	17	8

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Facebook	14	6
Family	28	13
Instagram	30	14
Insurance Websites	23	10
Twitter	15	7

Social media platforms, along with family and friends, are the primary sources of awareness, highlighting the importance of digital communication and personal networks in influencing individuals' knowledge and adoption of fintech-based insurance services.

Table: 2 Types of insurance purchased by respondents

Particulars	Insured	Not aware, but insured	Not Insured	Not aware & not insured
Health	63	30	18	24
Home	46	15	46	28
Life	83	9	29	14
Vehicle	52	16	40	27

Life and health insurance are the most adopted, while some respondents lack complete awareness despite being insured, indicating fintech's role in increasing coverage but also the need for better customer education and clarity.

Table: 3 Claim experience of respondents

Satisfaction Level	Highly Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Highly Satisfied
Speed of claim processing	3	52	34	32	14
Documentation	3	17	42	54	19
Payment methods	1	12	37	59	26
Timely Updates	5	26	43	44	17

Respondents show mixed satisfaction levels, with positive feedback on documentation and payment methods, but concerns regarding slow claim processing and delayed updates, indicating the need for improvement in efficiency and service quality.

Table: 4 Challenges faced by Respondents

Particulars	Yes	No	Sometimes
Abs. of face to face support	73	40	22
High premium	44	40	51
Lack of information	27	58	50

Particulars	Yes	No	Sometimes
Slow claim process	55	43	37
Technical issues	43	38	54
Trust issues	49	48	38
Unaware of technology	40	52	43
Usage of mobile phone	64	40	31

Major challenges include lack of face-to-face interaction, technical issues, slow claim processing, trust concerns, and limited digital knowledge, suggesting the need for better support systems, user education, and improved technological infrastructure.

Tabel 5: Comparison of digital insurance over traditional insurance

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Prefer Digital	27	20
Prefer Digital	41	30
Neutral	26	19
Prefer Offline	17	13
Strongly Prefer Offline	24	18

While a significant number of respondents prefer digital insurance due to convenience and accessibility, some still prefer offline methods, indicating resistance to change and the need for awareness programs to encourage digital adoption.

Cross Tabulation

Cross tabulation with the Chi-Square test is a statistical method used to examine the relationship or association between two categorical variables, where cross tabulation presents data in a table format showing how the categories of one variable are distributed across the categories of another variable, while the Chi-Square test checks whether the observed relationship between the variables is statistically significant or not. Data are first collected through surveys or questionnaires and classified into categorical variables such as age, education, income, awareness level, or usage of financial products, after which a cross table is prepared by placing one variable in rows and the other in columns, and the frequencies of responses are entered into the table. After forming the cross tabulation, the Chi Square test is applied to determine whether the differences observed between the variables are due to chance or represent a real association.

Online platforms used for insurance

H₀: There is no association between demographic profile of the individual and criteria for assessing impact on it.

Table: 6 Cross tabulation of online insurance platforms with age

Sr.No	Particulars	Chi-Square value	Pearson Value	Remark
1.	Company websites	6.394	0.172	H0 is accepted
2.	Web aggregates	0.661	0.956	H0 is accepted
3.	Digital wallets	4.687	0.321	H0 is accepted
4.	Other related factors	3.520	0.475	H0 is accepted

Table: 7 Cross tabulation of online insurance platforms with income

Sr.No	Particulars	Chi-Square value	Pearson Value	Remark
1.	Company websites	4.151	0.386	H0 is accepted
2.	Web aggregates	13.430	0.009	H0 is rejected
3.	Digital wallets	5.288	0.259	H0 is accepted
4.	Other related factors	3.940	0.414	H0 is accepted

Table: 8 Cross tabulation of online insurance platforms with education

Sr.No	Particulars	Chi-Square value	Pearson Value	Remark
1	Company websites	0.864	0.930	H0 is accepted
2.	Web aggregates	1.529	0.821	H0 is accepted
3.	Digital wallets	5.474	0.242	H0 is accepted
4.	Other related factors	5.696	0.223	H0 is accepted

The present study investigates the association between demographic characteristics and the utilization of online insurance platforms using chi-square analysis. The findings reveal that age and education do not exhibit any statistically significant association with platform usage, as all computed p-values exceed the threshold level of 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. In contrast, income demonstrates a statistically significant relationship with the use of web aggregator platforms ($p = 0.009$), resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis for this specific variable. However, no significant association is observed between income and other platforms such as company websites, digital wallets, and related factors. These findings imply that while most demographic variables do not significantly influence platform preference, income plays a selective and meaningful role in shaping the adoption of web aggregators.

Challenges in FinInsure

H₀: There is no impact of demographic profile and challenges for FinInsure

Table: 9 Cross Tabulation between Age and Challenges in FinInsure

Sr. No	Particulars	Chi-Square value	Pearson Value	Remark
1.	High premium	5.754	0.675	H ₀ is accepted
2.	Lack of information	10.938	0.534	H ₀ is accepted
3.	Trust issues	9.934	0.270	H ₀ is accepted
4.	Slow claim	6.297	0.614	H ₀ is accepted
5.	Unaware of technology	11.284	0.186	H ₀ is accepted
6.	Technical issues	11.031	0.200	H ₀ is accepted
7.	Abs. of face-to-face support	12.464	0.132	H ₀ is accepted
8.	Usage of mobile phone	17.044	0.030	H ₀ is rejected

Table: 10 Cross Tabulation between Income and Challenges in FinInsure

Sr. No	Particulars	Chi-Square value	Pearson Value	Remark
1.	High premium	11.499	0.175	H ₀ is accepted
2.	Lack of information	12.999	0.369	H ₀ is accepted
3.	Trust issues	5.860	0.663	H ₀ is accepted
4.	Slow claim	8.944	0.347	H ₀ is accepted
5.	Unaware of technology	5.329	0.722	H ₀ is accepted
6.	Technical issues	15.507	0.050	H ₀ is accepted
7.	Abs. of face-to-face support	8.099	0.424	H ₀ is accepted
8.	Usage of mobile phone	2.606	0.957	H ₀ is accepted

Table: 11 Cross Tabulation between Education and Challenges in FinInsure

Sr. No	Particulars	Chi-Square value	Pearson Value	Remark
1.	High premium	7.733	0.460	H ₀ is accepted
2.	Lack of information	9.721	0.640	H ₀ is accepted
3.	Trust issues	9.172	0.328	H ₀ is accepted
4.	Slow claim	9.170	0.328	H ₀ is accepted
5.	Unaware of technology	12.478	0.131	H ₀ is accepted
6.	Technical issues	12.061	0.149	H ₀ is accepted
7.	Abs. of face-to-face support	6.995	0.537	H ₀ is rejected
8.	Usage of mobile phone	10.734	0.217	H ₀ is accepted

The results of the chi-square analysis indicate that demographic variables have a limited influence on the challenges faced by respondents while using FinInsure platforms. Age does

not exhibit a significant association with most identified challenges; however, a statistically significant relationship is observed with mobile phone usage ($p < 0.05$), suggesting differences in digital adaptability across age groups. Similarly, income shows no significant association with any of the challenges, indicating uniformity in user experience across income levels. In the case of education, no significant relationships are found for most factors, except for the absence of face-to-face support, which demonstrates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Overall, the findings suggest that challenges in FinInsure adoption are largely independent of demographic characteristics, with only marginal variations observed in specific aspects.

Findings

The study on “FinTech Innovations and their Transformative Impact on Individuals for Financial Protection through Insurance” demonstrates that FinTech has become a key driver of transformation in the insurance sector. The integration of advanced digital technologies has made insurance services more efficient, transparent, and widely accessible, eliminating traditional barriers such as geographical limitations, complex paperwork, and dependency on intermediaries. This has significantly strengthened financial protection for individuals.

FinTech tools like artificial intelligence, mobile applications, big data analytics, and cloud computing have enhanced customer engagement by enabling insurers to offer personalized and customer-centric products. This shift has improved affordability, suitability, and encouraged individuals to adopt insurance as a proactive financial planning tool. Additionally, automation in processes such as policy issuance, premium collection, and documentation has increased operational efficiency, reduced costs, and improved service delivery, thereby building greater customer trust.

However, the study also identifies challenges including claim settlement delays, cybersecurity risks, technical issues, and limited digital literacy. Lack of personal interaction during critical stages may also affect customer satisfaction. Therefore, a balanced integration of technology and human support, along with stronger security measures and effective regulations, is essential to ensure inclusive growth, sustainability, and enhanced financial resilience in the digital insurance ecosystem.

5. CONCLUSION

The study highlights that FinTech has emerged as a transformative force in the insurance sector, significantly improving efficiency, transparency, and accessibility. By integrating

digital technologies, traditional insurance systems have evolved beyond geographical limitations, complex paperwork, and intermediary dependence, thereby strengthening financial protection for individuals.

Innovations such as artificial intelligence, mobile applications, big data analytics, and cloud computing have enhanced customer engagement by enabling insurers to design personalized and customer-focused products. This transition from standardized offerings to tailored solutions has improved affordability and encouraged individuals to consider insurance as an essential financial planning tool. Additionally, automation of processes like policy issuance, premium collection, and documentation has streamlined operations, reduced costs, and improved service delivery, leading to greater customer trust and transparency.

However, the study also identifies ongoing challenges, including delays in claim settlement, cybersecurity concerns, technical issues, and limited digital literacy among certain groups. The lack of personal interaction during crucial stages such as claims and grievance handling may also affect customer satisfaction. To address these issues, a balanced approach combining technology and human support is necessary. Strengthening data security, improving claim management systems, enhancing digital awareness, and ensuring effective regulatory frameworks will be crucial. Overall, FinTech-driven insurance is paving the way for a more inclusive, efficient, and resilient financial protection system.

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